

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

INTERPRETATION OF THE "SUBJECT CONTENT BLOCK ELEMENTS" OF THE FOREIGN LANGUAGE SUBJECT CURRICULUM AT THE GENERAL EDUCATION LEVEL BASED ON THE "SYSTEM-STRUCTURE" APPROACH

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Abstract

In the article, it is emphasized that the curriculum reform is conditioned by the need to ensure the adequacy of the implementation of education to the challenges of the 21st century, to cultivate a creative, self-developing personality, and the content of the abilities necessary to become the subject of a student who has completed his general education is shown.

In the research work, the basis of the basis of the "system-structure" approach in the practical activity of the educator both in accordance with the essence of the "General education program" and in his educational program, the field of auxiliary science implemented on the basis of the curricula of the subjects, the potential related to the systems of economic concepts, is directly drawn to the center of attention directed to the mastery of these concepts.

In the article, the structure of the foreign language subject curriculum at the general education level is interpreted on the basis of the "system-structure" dialectical approach of the general learning outcomes, content lines, learning results by content lines, content standards, integration concepts, which are included in the "Subject Content Block" of the "block-scheme" form. is presented.

Keywords. Educational program; curriculum; education plan; content line; content standards; sentence constructions; reading technique; pronunciation rules.

Relevance of the research topic

Observations show that in the activities of educators, mistakes are made in the application of the foreign language subject curriculum at the general education level. This has a negative effect on the level of efficiency of the foreign language teaching process.

It is undeniable that the level of understanding of any real thing has a determining effect on the results of using it in adequate directions. On the basis of our scientific observations over the past ten years, we have come to the conclusion that the mistakes manifested in the activities of practical educators in the process of using the foreign language subject curriculum are based on a number of reasons, as well as a lack of honest understanding of the essence of the foreign language subject curriculum by these subjects. Based on our experience in the field of scientific activity, we claim that the "system-structure" approach is the most reliable dialectical method of understanding any existing thing and getting to its essence. The analysis of the materials we have collected gives reason to say that this method is insufficiently used in the theoretical and technological directions regarding the discovery of the essence of the foreign language subject curriculum and the determination of its application methods. Therefore, we claim that the "interpretation of the subject content block elements" of the foreign language subject curriculum at

the general education level based on the "system-structure" approach is a relevant research topic.

Interpretation of generalizations formed on the basis of research materials

It is known that "in the 21st century, the main value in the life and development of both society and each of its members is a creative, self-developing personality." [13; 16] and education cannot exist outside the realities of a changing world. It is not accidental that "modern psychology considers the creation of favorable conditions for the discovery and realization of a child's creative abilities to be the main goal of education." [6; 290-292] Therefore, since the main value in the modern period is a creative, self-developing personality, the educational process should form creativity and self-development abilities in the child. This, in turn, is based on the following activity, understanding needs and abilities: 1) logical thinking; 2) critical approach to objects and events of the surrounding world; 3) making decisions independently; 4) change the surroundings at a creative speed; 5) independent acquisition of knowledge; 6) solving practical problems; 7) setting new goals for personality development, etc. Notwithstanding the foregoing, a student who has completed general education must be able to: to analyze the texts of different styles and genres that he listened to and read, to convey their content to someone else in a

concise and partially broad form; to use monologue and dialogue forms of speech; preparing a plan, thesis, overview, project, opinion; to logically justify their ideas through examples and evidence, to summarize the main points expressed in different ideas; perform calculations and programming, use mathematical language, to build algorithms, to make assumptions; to use the methods and means of observation, measurement, calculation, experiment, evaluation to understand the surrounding world; to explain the nature of the basic regularities in nature and their interrelation; to compare, classify and present various facts, opinions and evidence; independently perform tasks that require creativity in the training process; to use different sources of information to perform training tasks; to consciously determine one's capabilities, inclination and interest, to demonstrate voluntary and involuntary qualities; to evaluate the results of his work; to follow public behavior, as well as relevant safety and medical-hygiene rules, healthy lifestyle norms; to demonstrate that he has national, moral, legal, aesthetic values, citizenship position, and leadership qualities; to work together in solving problems, to evaluate the performance of oneself and others in the collective work process; to communicate in a foreign language, etc.

The listed skills of a student who has completed his general education, that is, the general learning results, are formed as a synthesis and dialectical unification of the results targeted in the process of teaching all subjects (including a foreign language) taught in general education schools.

It is undeniable that it is of particular importance for the foreign language teacher to honestly know the tasks set before the general education (general expected results). However, this is one side of the issue and it is necessary to put the activity related to the educational process into a result-oriented system. Thus, the goal is a system-creating component in all processes. In addition, it is very important to implement the training process in what content, based on which strategy, and based on which assessment mechanisms, in order to achieve the goal. "The new necessary minimum of training for the levels of general education, the knowledge limit, the general learning results for the subject and the learning results to be obtained at the individual levels of general education (subsystems of the general education implementation system) in advance of the skills to be acquired (*which these results are as components of the expected general results is included* - italics are ours) is considered one of the most important problems of education". [10;71]

As is known, the teacher should be able to find both theoretical and practical answers to all questions related to the learning process. He should know which model he uses in the process of which he is a facilitator and what specific features this model has. This model combines the advantages of traditional models (It should not be forgotten that innovation is not a complete denial of the old, such denial can bring more harm than good) and what success it promises to the real pedagogical process.

Based on what we have said, we summarize that the main features of the educational program (curriculum), which is currently applied in general education schools "which is understood as a conceptual document that enables the effective organization of all activities related to the educational process, purposeful and consistent implementation" [7;228-229] It would be beneficial for the overall work to give an interpretation based on the "system-structure" approach.

The teacher is one of the leading subjects in the implementation of the educational program. The level of his penetration into the essence of the mentioned program has a conditioning effect on the effectiveness of its activity. Therefore, it is important to refer to the "system-structure" approach both in getting to know the essence of the program and in the practical activities related to its implementation, the analysis of research materials and our work experience brings us to this conclusion.

It should be emphasized here that the essence of the system is determined by its structure and function, that is, by the nature of the relationship between the elements and their behavior, and by the specificity of the relationship between the object and the conditions. Without studying the elements that make up the system and their interaction, it is impossible to distinguish the continuous, important and necessary relationships here. Such continuous, important and necessary interaction of elements characterizes the structure of the system. The law of relationships of structural elements acts as an invariant of the system. Without learning and opening the relationship of the elements with the whole formed by them, both the function of the system and the functions of each element with regard to the whole remain in the shadows. The full concept is understood in terms of the system, it is the organization of that system. Each system has its own structure and the function that this structure carries. A system can be viewed as a whole consisting of the unity of its structure and function. Systems differ from each other not only by their structure and functions, but also mainly by the nature of the unity of structure and function, the nature of this unity.

The educational program (curriculum) determines the content of education and the rules of mastering it at different levels and levels of education in accordance with the state educational standards. [8; 106-107] The educational program includes the curriculum, educational programs for subjects, recommendations on methodical provision, assessment and other relevant educational technologies. [7;173] Listed are subsystems of the Education program. Educational programs (curriculums) are divided into two parts according to their nature: functional and personality-oriented.

Science-oriented curricula are directly oriented to the assimilation of these concepts by covering the field of science and its perfect system of concepts in terms of content. Personality-oriented curricula are distinguished by their direct emphasis on life skills and habits. "Personality-oriented", "pupil-oriented" and "result-oriented" approaches of the curriculum show that the student is at the center of the learning process. [12] These approaches are reflected, in particular, in the

writing of learning objectives. The highlighted features of the curriculum have a great benefit in the educational process: it makes the educational process more efficient, it enables the formation of experience-oriented skills. In this regard, new demands are placed on the teacher. [2; 174]

The main components of curriculum education are the recognition of the uniqueness of each student's activity, including the learning activity. In personality-oriented education, the student acts as the central figure of the entire learning process, the teacher acts as a guide and assistant in the individual development of the student. Here, the teacher's task is not to convey knowledge, but to organize an environment for the student that provides learning technology appropriate to his potential capabilities. Personality orientation is the formation of national and human values in students by developing their life skills based on cognitive, communication and psychomotor activities. Student-centeredness is the fact that activities in the field of education serve the interests of students, satisfy their interests

and needs, develop their talents, abilities, and potential opportunities. Results orientation is the pre-determination of intended learning achievements in the form of results. Demand-oriented - consideration of the changing needs and demands of the individual, society and the state.

Subject curricula: take a balanced and comprehensive approach to learning different skills; enables achievement of content standards using active learning methods; implies constant assessment of students' knowledge and understanding, making corrections during the academic year; ensures involvement of students in training, preparation and motivation for continuous education; it envisages the use of modern technologies when students are studying, evaluating their knowledge, and increasing their literacy; has adequate training resources and administrative support. [3; 158-161]

The block diagram form of the subject curriculum structure can be drawn as follows: [8; 38] (see Scheme 1):

Scheme 1

Summing up, it can be said that the foreign language subject curriculum is a conceptual document of interest to students, teachers, parents and other members of society, it covers the goals of foreign language learning and all activities to achieve these goals. This document aims to develop the speech, language skills and habits of each student, taking into account their interests and inclinations. As can be seen from the presented scheme, the document in question defines the main objectives of foreign language teaching in general education schools, general learning outcomes, content lines, learning outcomes by content lines, content standards, intra-disciplinary and interdisciplinary integration, training strategies, requirements, forms and

methods for training organization. contains recommendations about. The foreign language curriculum is built on the basis of principles from simple to complex, from easy to difficult in accordance with result-oriented content standards, including the formation of communicative language skills based on language and socio-cultural knowledge, and provides an opportunity to monitor and evaluate student achievements.

As stated in the framework document of the National Curriculum of general education in the Republic of Azerbaijan, through the teaching of a foreign language: listening comprehension, oral speech, formation of initial writing skills, creation and development of correct reading skills are ensured at the level of primary education; taking the development of oral speech as the

main requirement at the secondary education level, forming students' communication skills, enriching vocabulary, mastering the most necessary grammatical concepts and language constructions, developing reading, writing techniques and written speech, and listening comprehension skills; by developing the activities intended for the full secondary level of education, students acquire communicative skills and culture of communication in a foreign language, enrich their vocabulary, arouse interest in learning a foreign language in depth, and expand their worldviews based on familiarity with the country (countries) in which they learn the language. [1]

In the process of defining content standards, the focus is on the expected balance of key learning outcomes (procedural skills, cognitive understanding, and problem solving) in the subject. [5; 454]

This curriculum presents key learning outcomes through the interrelationship of content and action lines to define what students 'should know' and 'do'. [13]

The document included in the "Introduction" block (the Curriculum can be interpreted as a collection of documents, this idea is based on scientific arguments) not only determines the place of a foreign language among the subjects taught in general education schools, but also allows to determine the main goals of its teaching in general. The main goal of foreign language training in secondary schools is defined as the formation of speech, language and communicative skills and habits. In order to achieve the specified goal, it is necessary to implement the following tasks: students acquire important linguistic (phonetic, orthographic, lexical, etc.) knowledge; introducing students to the culture and traditions of the countries where the language is studied, forming their ability to represent their country and its culture in a foreign language and intercultural environment; development of communicative skills in speech activity; formation and development of language perception, all types of memory, logical, critical and creative thinking (analysis, comparison, generalization, drawing conclusions, etc.); education of citizenship qualities, respect for other cultures. [4;40-41]

Students who have completed the general education level acquire the following learning outcomes: read the text expressively, determine its stylistic character and main idea; reads the text presented for the first time and contains up to 5-10 percent unknown words using a dictionary and explains its content; uses simple and complex sentence constructions in translation. [1]

As it is known, in the "Subject content block" (We can consider it as a subsystem contained in the foreign language subject curriculum block scheme.) the content line is the part of the content that is considered necessary to ensure the realization of the general learning results of the subject. Content lines are defined to more clearly describe the content that students will learn and aim to systematize it. We can interpret content lines in another way: Content lines have the function of realizing the goals and tasks set in foreign language learning. Content lines are subsystems of the content that is de-

signed to be mastered in the subject of a foreign language, existing in a dialectical unity, these are relatively separated parts of the content.

Based on the study and analysis of the current world experience, the following content lines of foreign language training were defined: 1. Listening and understanding; 2. Speaking; 3. Reading; 4. Writing.

It should be emphasized that four content lines are distinguished in the mother tongue subject curriculum. Here, the first content line contains "Listening, understanding and speaking", and the fourth content line is formulated as "Language rules". As it can be seen, the differentiation of the classifications of content lines in the mother tongue and foreign language subject curricula results from the "enabling functions" of these subjects as a subsystem in the "General Education Program" system.

The content lines of the foreign language subject also serve to design the structure of the curriculum and to reflect on it. It should be noted that any concepts or skills included in the content of the subject may not be limited to only one content line. When determining content lines, it is assumed that each of them will be given equal importance in the process of teaching a foreign language subject.

We agree that curriculum based on content lines covers a wide range of content. This broad content, taught in an integrative manner, allows students to understand the interrelationship of different knowledge of the subject, not only within the subject of a foreign language, but also in other subjects and in real life.

Scientific sources emphasize that the content standard is a state requirement for the level of knowledge and skills of the student. [3;468] The standards for the subject of foreign language cover the content that is important for all students within the secondary education course, describe the knowledge and skills of students in foreign language, determine the issues that every student in the country can and should learn in the field of foreign language, and prepare students for the next level of education. The content standards are integrative learning outcomes that ensure that students move through the levels as they achieve appropriate knowledge, skills, and values.

The new approach to setting the content of the standards envisages that each standard consists of several defined objectives (sub-standards) and is repeated throughout the grades in an appropriately expanding capacity. The parent standard should be viewed as a system, and substandards should be considered substandards of the parent standard as appropriate. It is in this approach that the main and substandards are able to carry their specific functions.

The content standards of the foreign language subject are systematized by classes and represented by the above four content lines. As highlighted above, the goal of each standard covers several expected learning outcomes identified at the elementary, middle and upper secondary levels, focuses on general expected outcomes of general education, and balances abilities such as cognitive understanding and problem solving. The components of foreign language teaching and learning

are not isolated from each other, on the contrary, they are related to each other and complement each other.

The function of the core standard is to explain the defined learning outcomes in a general way along the content lines. It is related to the functions of sub-standards: it creates a reliable basis for the precise determination of learning objectives; plays an important role in the correct selection of training strategies; ensures integration in training; ensures continuous development of training content; provides summative assessment for classes and subjects.

Realization of content standards for the foreign language subject is carried out along the following lines of action: 1) solving problems; 2) justification; 3) communication; 4) research; 5) implementation.

While action lines are distinct from content lines, they are related to each of them. These lines aim to define and describe the ways of acquiring and using content knowledge and serve to make students understand the importance of foreign language subject and view it

as a set of complex skills. Action lines should be understood as subsystems of the learner's activity system, and the emergent nature of the "containing system" and the dialectic of relations between the subsystems should be focused on in their application.

The student can achieve the content he will learn from the foreign language subject through various activities. Different stages of the student's activity in the process of mastering the content ensure that the acquired knowledge and skills are more solid and long-lasting. Performance standards ensure students mastery of content standards for curriculum implementation. Each performance standard describes what is covered in the grade and what the teacher's role is in achieving the content standard. It should be noted that each performance standard varies across educational levels and grades, with use in all grades. Therefore, it is convenient to adopt these standards in general.

Knowledge and activity components of the content standards, their classification is as follows: (see scheme 2)

Scheme 2

Curriculum theorists have identified verbs that express all stages of all three taxonomies (cognitive, emotional, psychomotor) considered useful for education in order to help standard developers (and educators involved in the educational implementation process).

Verbs are a very important indicator in expressing skills. The verb reflects which phase of the skill's taxonomy it belongs to. These can be expressed as follows: [8; 41] (see: table 1,2,3)

Table1

Cognitive taxonomy	
Stage	Performance indicators
Don't know	Remembering, remembering, recognizing, recalling
Understanding	Explanation, conversion of the matter from one means of expression to another means of expression, description in one's own words
Implementation	Problem solving, applying information to achieve certain results
Analysis	Break down, divide, find the structure that forms the basis of communication to show how it exists together; identifying motives.
Synthesis	Creation of a unique (unique, original, initial) product, which can be both verbal and physical object
Evaluation	Making important decisions about the issue; resolving disputes or differences of opinion

Table 2

Emotional taxonomy	
Stage	Performance indicators
Acceptance	The student is encouraged to participate in any learning process. Issues in these standards develop it from understanding the presence of an item to a selective approach.
Don't react	The student actively participates in the learning process, answers questions and reacts to events. In these standards, the student's tastes and interests are sought and applied in activities.
Evaluation	It helps the student to evaluate any object or event. These standards create conditions for analyzing the attitude to what happened.
Organization	The standards that serve to form the student's outlook are based on this stage.
Reflecting a value or value system in character	At this stage, the individual has a system of values that controls his behavior and determines his lifestyle. These content standards help in the formation of personal, social and emotional behavior of the student.

Table 3

Psychomotor taxonomy	
Stage	Performance indicators
Verb	Before the action is carried out, the moral state is regulated
Get ready	It is the stage of preparation for the execution of special actions
Simulate	It is used in the initial stage of training complex habits.
Mechanism	Demonstrates self-confidence during performance.
Perfect execution	Demonstrates complex activities formed as perfect habits.
Adaptation	Individuals make changes in their behavior in order to control a problematic situation or to adapt to specific demands.
Creativity	A new type of activity is created that responds to a specific situation or problem.

Taxonomies make learning more consistent and efficient. Taxonomies play a major role in the learning process. They provide the following opportunities: correctly define training goals; correctly define problems and design tasks for students; choose evaluation tools according to the set goals; properly conduct reflection based on learning outcomes; to determine what difficulties students face in learning this or that material.

The formation of knowledge, skills and habits that students can acquire and apply in their daily lives in the educational process requires the teaching of both these subjects and the topics covered by them in a connected - integrative manner. Integration - within the framework of a certain educational system, to form a whole and indivisible image of the world in the thinking of students, to direct them to development and self-development, to establish structural connections between all content components of training and to systematize them. In itself, this process serves to create a whole and complete image of the world through sciences that study the surrounding world from different aspects.

Rapid social, cultural and technological changes in the modern world greatly increase the importance of a global mindset. In this case, in the learning process, students are not passive consumers of the knowledge and skills given in individual subjects, but on the contrary, it leads to being treated as subjects who have a creative attitude towards understanding the world around them. This is possible when the subjects studied at the educational levels (these are subsystems with the "enabling function" in educational programs) and the topics covered by them are taught not separately, but in a connected - integrative manner.

Current world experience shows that it is impossible to achieve the desired (desired) result in the teaching of any subject, including foreign language, without using various integration methods in the learning process. Thus, the role of integration in stimulating training, ensuring students' activity, mastering the intended content in detail, and shaping the scientific worldview of students is undeniable. In general, integration is the systematization of content components of training based on structural relationships. Several types of integration are applied in the field of education.

Interdisciplinary integration involves the integration of understanding, knowledge and skills in each subject. In other words, this type of integration is the systematization of knowledge, skills and habits for the creation of connections within the discipline and the achievement of learning outcomes. Intra-subject integration determines the content structure of the subject by concentrating the teaching material in separate teaching units. In this way, it is ensured that the content is informative and students have more comprehensive skills.

Intra-subject integration is widely used in foreign language teaching. The intra-disciplinary integration of the foreign language subject is ensured through the interaction of content lines, basic standards and sub-standards, in other words, "system-structural relations" are expected here. Sub-systems and elements are subject to the nature of the whole they are contained in, and exist with dialectical relations among themselves, they realize the "capacity-carrying functions". The relationship between content lines can be schematically described as follows: (see: Scheme 3)

Scheme 3

It is known that interdisciplinary integration is the synthesis of common concepts, knowledge and skills covered by several disciplines, and it takes into account the use of concepts and methods of one discipline in the study of another discipline. At this time, the teaching of subjects related to different subjects, but complementary to each other, including similar ones, is put into a certain framework. Therefore, it is important to determine the relationships between different subjects and topics, and to creatively use these relationships in the formation of interdisciplinary understanding and skills.

Scientific novelty and theoretical significance of the research work

1) The importance of the application of the "system-structure" approach method, which was formed as an important branch of the dialectic regarding the discovery of the essence of the foreign language subject curriculum and the determination of its application methods, was brought to the attention of the researchers; 2) The solution of one of the cognitive issues that determines the solution to the problem of revealing the essence of the foreign language subject curriculum at the general education level and developing its application in the optimal version - the interpretation of the "subject content block elements" based on the "system-structure" approach" was presented.

Practical significance of the research work

We hope that the solution of one of the important cognitive issues that determines the solution to the problem of uncovering the essence of the foreign language subject curriculum applied at the level of general education and the optimal implementation of its application - the presentation of the "interpretation of the subject content block elements" based on the "system-structural" approach" of the foreign language subject curriculum. The elimination of mistakes manifested in the activities

of educators in the application of the curriculum will have a positive effect on the formation of the environment.

The result

1) The level of understanding of any real thing has a determining effect on the results of taking advantage of it in adequate directions. 2) Making mistakes in the activities of educators in the application of the foreign language subject curriculum at the general education level has a negative effect on the efficiency level of the teaching process of this subject; 3) In the process of using the foreign language subject curriculum, at the basis of the mistakes manifested in the activities of practical educators, there is a lack of honest enough understanding of the essence of the foreign language subject curriculum by these subjects; 4) "System-structure" approach is the most reliable dialectical method of understanding any existing thing, getting to its essence; 5) The dialectical method of the "system-structure" approach regarding the discovery of the essence of the foreign language subject curriculum and the determination of its application methods was not used in theoretical and technological directions; 6) One of the cognitive issues aimed at solving the problem that creates the basis for the manifestations of the error caused by the "gap" regarding the discovery of the essence of the foreign language subject curriculum and the determination of the ways of its application is based on the "system-structure" approach of the "Subject content block elements" of the foreign language subject curriculum at the general education level. interpretation" and our research summary presented in this direction benefits the process of foreign language teaching.

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ТАЪЛИМ КЛАСТЕРИ МУҲИТИДА БЎЛАЖАК ЖИСМОНИЙ ТАРБИЯ ЎҚИТУВЧИЛАРИНИНГ КРЕАТИВ КОМПЕТЕНТЛИГИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ЖАРАЁНЛАРИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ БЎЙИЧА ЎТКАЗИЛГАН ТАЖРИБА-СИНОВЛАР

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PILOT TESTING TO IMPROVE THE PROCESSES OF DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF PHYSICAL CULTURE IN THE ENVIRONMENT OF THE EDUCATIONAL CLUSTER

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Аннотация

Мақолада жисмоний маданиятнинг моҳияти, унинг тузилиши, турлари, услублари, воситалари, самарадорлик омиллари, алоқа ва фаолият, унинг мезонлари жисмоний тарбия фанини ўқитиш санъати бўйича аудиториядан ташқари дарсларнинг муаллифлик дастури мисолида олий таълим муассасалари талабаларини самарали ўқитиш технологияси ва техникасига тайёрлаш учун маҳаллий модулли технологиялар ишлаб чиқарилиши ва амалиётга татбиқ этилиши сўз этилган.

Abstract

In the article, the essence of physical culture, its structure, types, methods, tools, efficiency factors, communication and activity, its criteria, as an example of the author's program of non-auditory classes on the art of teaching physical education, the development of local modular technologies to prepare students of higher educational institutions for effective teaching technology and techniques issued and put into practice.

Калит сўзлар: Таълим, жисмоний маданият, муҳит, тарбия, ўқитувчи, услуб, омил, санъат, талаба, ўқитиш, технология, дастур, модул, муассаса, мезон, аудитория, дарс.

Keywords: Education, physical culture, environment, upbringing, teacher, method, factor, art, student, teaching, technology, program, module, institution, criterion, audience, lesson.

Таълим тизими дунё тараққиётининг асосий ҳаракатлангирувчи кучи ва барқарор ривожланишнинг муҳим омил сифатида қаралади. Уни такомиллаштириш ва сифатли ташкил қилиш, таълим олувчиларга қафолатланган билим бериш механизмларини ўқув-машғулотлар жараёнига жорий қилиш устивор йўналишлардан бири

ҳисобланади. Етакчи таълим муассасалари томонидан бўлажак кадрларни ўқитишда инновацион педагогик технологияларни ишлаб чиқиш ва амалиётга жорий этиш юзасида кўплаб тадқиқотлар амалга оширилмоқда.

Жаҳонда бўлажак жисмоний тарбия ўқитувчилари аҳолининг бошқа ижтимоий